

THE EFFECT OF MOISTURE ON THE INTERFACIAL STRENGTH OF GRAPHITE-EPOXY AND E-GLASS-EPOXY COMPOSITES

W. L. Bradley, C. A. Wood, B.A. Pratt, and C. S. Chatawanich

*Department of Mechanical Engineering and Offshore Technology Research Center
Texas A&M University, College Station, TX 77843-3123, USA*

SUMMARY: The effect of absorbed moisture on the fiber/matrix interfacial strength and 90° ply strength have been studied for E-glass and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy. Single fiber fragmentation tests have indicated a 19% reduction in the interfacial strength in carbon/epoxy composites which absorbed 1.4% of their matrix weight in seawater. Micro indentation measurement on E-glass/epoxy composites indicated a 25% reduction in the interfacial shear strength when the absorbed seawater increased from 1.2 to 2.2% of the matrix weight. In-situ observations of fracture in an environmental scanning electron microscope with associated calculations indicated reductions in interfacial strength ranging from 0 to 30%, with 2/3rds attributed to reductions in interfacial strength and the balance due to changes in the residual thermal stresses.

KEYWORDS: polymeric composites, carbon, E-glass, epoxy, seawater, interfacial strength, microindentation, single fiber fragmentation test

INTRODUCTION

The prospect of large oil reserves at 2000m of ocean depth has created a significant interest in the possibility of using polymeric composite tubulars for both drilling risers and production risers. The higher specific strength of polymeric composite material systems can potentially allow conventional equipment designed for drilling and oil production using floating ships and platforms for depths of <1000m to be used at these greater depths by reducing the hanging weight of the tubulars. The potential use of polymeric matrix composites for offshore applications has been recently reviewed [1] and the economic feasibility of using polymeric composite tubulars for production risers has already been demonstrated [2].

Polymeric matrix composites are known to have excellent fatigue resistance, do not corrode, and can be tailored to give optimal combinations of stiffness, strength, and thermal expansion by proper ply sequencing. The two technical obstacles to the use of polymeric composite materials for offshore risers are joining and long-term durability. While polymeric composite materials do not corrode like metals, they do absorb moisture, generally 1-3% of the weight of the matrix. This absorbed moisture can potentially soften the matrix, reduce the strength of the glass fibers (carbon fibers appear to be unaffected by moisture), and/or degrade the strength of the fiber matrix interface. Since production risers will be immersed continuously for 10-20 years, they will certainly reach saturation levels of moisture absorption eventually. Thus, the effect of the absorbed moisture on long term durability needs to be determined.

The purpose of this study has been to investigate effect of the absorbed moisture on the interfacial strength of several polymeric composite material systems. Direct observations of the initiation of damage in the systems investigated in this study indicate that the failure scenario begins with interfacial failure by debonding leading to transverse cracking, and subsequently, delamination. Absorbed moisture can perturb this failure scenario by reducing the chemical adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface, relaxing the residual compressive stresses at the fiber/matrix interface, reducing the ply level residual tensile stresses in the 90° plies, and toughening the polymeric matrix. Since these various effects of absorbed moisture can potentially postpone interfacial failure or cause it to occur prematurely, a more careful study has been undertaken to determine the effect of absorbed moisture on the interfacial strength and on the ply level mechanical stress at which interfacial failure leading to transverse cracking occurs.

To determine the effect of absorbed moisture on the initiation of ply level damage in a multi axial laminate, micro indentation tests [3] and tensile tests in-situ in an environmental scanning electron microscope have been performed on specimens as received and specimens aged in seawater until a saturation level of moisture absorption has occurred. Single fiber fragmentation tests [4] have also been used to investigate the effect of absorbed moisture on the interfacial shear strength.

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES

Two polymeric composite material systems have been studied in this investigation: (a) a Shell 828 epoxy (DGEBA), cured at 398K with meta-phenylene diamine (mPDA), reinforced with E-glass type 30 Owens Corning fibers and (b) a proprietary diglycidyl ether bisphenal-A (DGEBA) with 5% rubber added for toughening, with a cure temperature of 422K, reinforced with E-glass fibers and graphite fibers (a hybrid composite). Two different sizings were used on the E-glass fibers in the 828 epoxy, one properly coated for compatibility with an epoxy matrix and the other coated for use with a vinyl ester. Hereafter, the 828 epoxy will be referred to as Epoxy 1 and the proprietary epoxy with 5% rubber additions will be referred to as Epoxy 2.

Single-fiber fragmentation test specimens were prepared by casting AS4 carbon fibers from Hercules in a dog bone shaped tensile specimen of Epoxy 2. Load and displacement measurements were made during testing using a load cell and an LVDT, with fiber breaks recorded using acoustic emission. Aging of specimens was done by emersion for 110 days in simulated seawater prepared from *Instant Ocean Mix* (purchased from a pet store). Other specimens were dried by heating in a vacuum furnace until the specimen weight stabilized. The moisture content for the three specimens tested were 0, 0.65 and 1.40% of the weight of the epoxy. The number of breaks as a function of strain was recorded and analyzed using the Kelly-Tyson approach [5]. Fiber strength was calculated using Weibull statistics applied to the single fiber fragmentation test itself, as suggested by Wagner [6]. The strain used to determine the stresses which were then used in the Weibull distribution was calculated from the mechanical strain applied to the specimen, the thermal cool down strain, and the swelling strain which occurs with moisture absorption. Additional information about the experimental details and analysis are presented in Reference 7.

Micro indentation tests were performed on Epoxy 1 reinforced with E-glass fibers in a laminate made from prepreg with a stacking sequence of $(\pm 45/90)_s$. Fiber volume fraction was 0.65 and curing was at 398K for 2 hours. One laminate was made using E-glass with a proper sizing for vinyl ester to see how sensitive to sizing is the moisture sensitivity of the interfacial strength. Some specimens were aged by soaking to saturation in simulated seawater prepared from *Instant Ocean Mix*. Weight gain was 1% of the matrix weight, for a total moisture content of 2.2%, since drying experiments indicated an initial moisture content as fabricated of 1.2% of the matrix weight. Testing was performed on a carefully polished surface using an Interfacial Testing System (ITS) manufactured by Dow Chemical. Since the debonding of glass fibers is gradual rather than at a single load, the debonding load was taken when debonding was $>90^\circ$ of the circumference of the fiber. The interfacial shear strength was determined using software which utilizes a linear elastic analysis [8]. During the testing of the aged specimens, it was necessary to keep the surface covered with seawater during the testing to avoid changes in the measurement due to dehydration of the specimens. Approximately 10 interfacial shear strength measurements were made on each specimen. Additional experimental details are summarized on Reference 8.

Tensile tests were performed in an environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM) to allow direct observations of the failure scenario of 90° plies. Special tensile specimens were prepared by grinding and polishing the edges of rectangular specimens 38mm long by 6mm wide, as seen in Figure 1. The reduced specimen width at the midpoint of the specimen length gives a maximum stress at this same location, causing the damage initiation to be sufficiently localized to allow it to be captured in the early stages. Getting a good metallographic polish on a curved surface required the development of some new polishing techniques. The aged specimens were tested in the ESEM with a 100% relative humidity to avoid dehydration during testing. Unaged specimens were tested at a much lower pressure and humidity in the ESEM. The specimens were loaded in displacement control, with both load and displacement monitored. The displacements were applied in step wise fashion, with careful surveying of the polished edge and photographic documentation of damage accumulation being done at each displacement step.

The laminate load measured at a given displacement was used to calculate the ply level stresses in the 90° plies at the initiation of debonding and at the first occurrence of transverse cracking using software based on classical laminate theory [9]. The ply level residual stresses on cool down to room temperature were also calculated using the same laminate analysis [9]. The residual stresses at the fiber/matrix interface were calculated using a micromechanics analysis based on linear elasticity called MICSTRAN [10,11]. MICSTRAN was also used to calculate the local stress concentration as a function of location around the circumference of the fiber/matrix interface as seen in Fig. 1c. Thus, the local radial stresses at the fiber matrix interface due to ply level mechanical and residual thermal stresses can be calculated. Alternatively, the residual thermal stresses at the fiber/matrix interface or the interfacial strength for debonding due to normal stressing could be converted into an equivalent ply level residual or critical stress.

Figure 1 a & b: The test geometry for specimens loaded to fracture in the ESEM, indicating the stacking sequence for the hybrid composites (E-glass and carbon/epoxy-2), (a) $[O_c 190_g]_s$

Figure 1c. Schematic showing the calculation of local radial stress at the fiber/matrix interface as a function of the ply level thermal and mechanical stresses

Figure 2a: Coalesced debonds adjacent to a resin rich region in an aged hybrid composite with carbon fibers in the 90⁰ ply

Figure 2b: Debonds adjacent to a void in E-glass/epoxy I composite

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Direct observations of fracture in the ESEM is seen in Figure 3. In the E-glass/epoxy 1 system, interfacial failures usually occurred first adjacent to local heterogeneities such as voids whereas in the carbon and E-glass/epoxy 2 system it occurred adjacent to local resin rich regions. In neither case was debonding found to be in a homogeneous region of the composite microstructure. Once debonding initiated in a local region, new debonds were found to take place adjacent to the original ones as the load is locally redistributed.

Figure 3: Interfacial shear strength determined from microindentation tests for E-glass/epoxy-1 system with an appropriate sizing for epoxy (158B) and a sizing for vinylesters (366), unaged (1.2% moisture), and aged (2.2% moisture)

Figure 4: Interfacial shear strength for carbon/epoxy-2 system with different levels of absorbed seawater, determined using single fiber fragmentation tests

A general observations of randomly arranged debonds which ultimately begin to coalesce when the local density reaches some critical level (like fiber failures) was never observed in any of the more than 50 tests run on a variety of specimens. It seems clear that debonding leading to transverse cracking is controlled by local heterogeneities and once initiated tends to

remain quite localized. Absorbed moisture was not found to affect the failure scenario, but only the load levels at which debonding began and transverse cracking ultimately was consummated.

The results of the Micro indentation tests to measure interfacial strength are presented in Figure 3 for the carbon/epoxy-2 system. The effect of moisture level as manufactured compared to artificially dried is seen to be insignificant. The absorbed moisture at a saturation of 1.4%, however, gives a reduction of 19%.

The interfacial shear strength in the E-glass/epoxy-1 system as measured by the micro indentation test is seen in Figure 4. Note that the E-glass with the proper 158B sizing had a better unaged interfacial strength and was less moisture sensitive, losing only 25% of its interfacial strength. On the other hand, the E-glass with the 366 sizing for vinyl esters lost more than 50% of its interfacial strength when saturated with seawater, indicating the importance of the use of a proper sizing for seawater immersion applications.

To analyze the interfacial stress at the fiber/matrix interface at which interfacial debonding occurs, the local stress at the fiber matrix interface was calculated beginning with the local stress due to ply level stress, as shown in Figure 1c, with the value of the stress concentration factor used being determined from MICSTRAN. Since almost all debonds were observed at the top or bottom of the fibers ($\theta = 90^\circ$), the local stress due to ply level mechanical and residual thermal stresses was evaluated at this position. The local interfacial residual thermal stress in the radial direction was also determined using MICSTRAN. Finally, the interfacial strength was calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_{22 \text{ int}} = (\sigma_{22 \text{ mech ply}} + \sigma_{22 \text{ resid ply}}) \times SC(\theta=90^\circ) + \sigma_{rr \text{ int th}} \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{22 \text{ mech ply}}$ and $\sigma_{22 \text{ resid ply}}$ are the mechanical stress due to external loading and the residual thermal stress due to differential thermal contraction during cool down (modified by moisture induced swelling) in the 90° ply, SC is the stress concentration factor relating local stress in the radial direction to ply level stress, and $\sigma_{rr \text{ int th}}$ is the local residual thermal stresses due to differential thermal contraction between the fiber and the matrix. It is worth noting that the ply level residual thermal stress is tensile in the 90° plies whereas the local residual thermal stress is compressive. Thus, one is helpful in postponing debonding whereas the other makes debonding easier. Both the local level residual thermal stress and the interfacial strength can be converted to equivalent ply level stresses using the stress concentration factor (SC), which is 1.45 for carbon fiber/epoxy and 1.82 for E-glass/epoxy. When the debonding occurs next to a spherical void, an additional stress concentration factor of 2.18 [13] needs to be multiplied times the 1.82 to calculate the local interfacial stress from ply level stresses or to calculate equivalent ply level stresses from the local thermal residual stresses or interfacial strength. Equation 1 can be rearranged to express the ply level mechanical stress at which debonding and subsequent transverse cracking occur, as follows:

$$\sigma_{22 \text{ mech ply}} = (\sigma_{rr \text{ int}} - \sigma_{rr \text{ int th}}) / SC - \sigma_{22 \text{ resid ply}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 5: The effect of absorbed seawater on the ply strength (lower, right) and on the interfacial strength, local residual thermal stress normal to the fiber/matrix interface and ply level thermal residual stress. Note the interfacial strength and local residual thermal stress are expressed in equivalent ply level stresses which are calculated by dividing the local values by an appropriate stress concentration factor, as described in the text

At transverse cracking, σ_{22} mech ply is the 90° ply strength and $\sigma_{r \text{ int}}$ is the interfacial strength for stresses applied normal to the fiber matrix interface. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 5 for all three systems. From an engineering point of view, the effect of the absorbed moisture on the mechanical stress level at which debonding and subsequent transverse cracking initiates is most important, and is presented in Fig. 5, lower right. The remaining three graphs allow one to infer the reasons for the observed changes in the allowable mechanical stress level in a seawater saturated polymeric composite. The absorbed moisture decreases the residual thermal stresses in the radial direction at the fiber/matrix interfacial, causing then to go net positive in two of the systems. However, the ply level residual thermal stresses which are tensile are relaxed by the absorbed seawater, which would give a greater ply level mechanical strength. In each of the systems studied, the combined effects of the residual thermal stresses at the ply level and the local interfacial level was to give a net decrease in the ply level mechanical strength of between 1.4 and 4.2 MPA in the three systems studied, or 6-8% of the respective unaged ply strength of the systems studied.

The reduction in interfacial strength resulted in a decrease in the ply strength ranging from essentially zero in the system with only 1.0% increase in seawater to 10.1 MPa, or 20% in the carbon/epoxy-2 system, which absorbed 1.3% seawater. It should be noted that the same system in the single fiber fragmentation test absorbed 1.4% seawater and gave a 19% reduction in the interfacial shear strength, which is surprisingly consistent, since one is measuring changes in interfacial strength for shear stressing and the other is measuring interfacial strength for stresses applied perpendicular to the fiber/matrix interface; however, the absolute values of the unaged and aged interfacial strengths are different, as one might expect. These results suggest that 2/3rds of the overall decrease in the critical strain (or stress) at which damage begins in 90° plies is due to moisture reduced changes in interfacial strength with the remaining 1/3rd due to changes in residual thermal stresses (at the ply and local level, combined).

The very low values of ply strength in the E-glass/epoxy-1 system were due to damage initiation always occurring at small, spherical voids in the microstructure which were introduced during processing. While the overall void content was less than 1%, these voids still dominated the failure process in the 90° plies. The low ply strength in the E-glass/epoxy-2 was due to the very high ply thermal stresses due to the very stiff adjacent 0° plies of carbon fiber. In the E-glass/epoxy-1 system, the plies adjacent to the 90s were ± 45 s of glass. In the graphite/epoxy-2 system, adjacent 0° plies were E-glass.

Finally, the values presented in Figure 5 should be consider illustrative, but only semi-quantitative since the residual thermal stresses were not calculated with a viscoelastic analysis but just used the room temperature modulus of the matrix. The stress concentration and thermal residual stresses calculated with MICSTRAN are dependent on the local fiber arrangement, with only diamond and square arrangement permitted. The actual fiber arrangements in the microstructure were more complicated and were generally neither square or diamond arrays.

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